

Bringing Deep Learning to the Enterprise!

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

AI has been all the rage in the past few years. Deep Learning is a specialized branch in AI that leverages Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) to model the computational graph. Enterprises are starting to adopt AI & Deep Learning applications in an effort to gain competitive advantage.

2. Aim

Deep Learning comprises of algorithms, which model the human brain. Through the use of relevant examples, the presentation will demonstrate that AI & Deep Learning are primed for the Enterprise with relevant examples of how this technology is driving novel use cases.

3. Material and methods

Deep Learning needs to be defined and the mathematics underlying need to be explained in succinct manner. Concepts such as Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD), Back propagation and related ideas need to be established.

In order to understand why Deep Learning is taking off, it is important to understand the drivers of this technology. The confluence of cheap storage, fast compute (GPUs) and advancement of statistical modeling techniques are enabling an exponential increase in applicability of Deep Learning algorithms such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs). Further we need to highlight the evolution of AI & Deep Learning libraries such as Tensorflow, Caffe, Torch, MXNet and Microsoft Cognitive Toolkit (CNTK) as a driving factor that dramatically simplifies the access to this technology.

4. Results

N/A

5. Conclusions

With evolving uses in Internet of Things (IoT), autonomous cars, Natural Language Processing (NLP) and computer vision, AI and Deep Learning has found the “killer” apps of the day. Now, these will start to disrupt the processes within the Enterprise.

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6. Keywords

AI, Machine Learning, Deep Learning, Neural Networks

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